

NOVEL PREHEATING METHOD WITH MATRIX RESIN IMPREGNATION FOR STAMP FORMING OF CFRTP

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber reinforced thermosetting resins (CFRTS) has been investigated as a promising lightweight material to reduce automotive weight significantly. On the other hand, carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP) has some advantages over CFRTS, regarding impact resistance, short molding cycle, secondary workability including weldability, and recyclability. Especially, CFRTP with common thermoplastics such as polypropylene or polyamide has great potential to be used for mass production automobile since their affordable price of raw materials.

However the last cost issues of such CFRTP which are caused by the high viscosity of thermoplastics are impregnation. Fully impregnated composite materials realize high cycle stamp forming, but such materials are too expensive for mass production automobile. Semi impregnated materials are relatively inexpensive, but are difficult to realize high cycle stamp forming. Additionally the current long preheating and blanking process before stamp forming is inefficient for mass production.

Therefore to improve the total heat efficiency drastically, we are developing new preheating machine which has the functions of blanking and preheating with impregnation by using semi impregnated prepreg. In this paper, we investigated the effect of the impregnation conditions by the vacuum press preheater on the mechanical properties of CFRTP.

1 INTRODUCTION

Many studies were conducted about impregnation of thermoplastic matrix resins to reinforcement fibers such as glass fibers and carbon fibers [1-3]. Thermoplastic resins have many advantages over thermosetting resins. But one of the biggest problem of them must be so much higher viscosity than thermosetting resins in making substrates with impregnation. Therefore former researches and activities were performed by using classical Darcy's law as Equation (1).

$$\frac{dx}{d\tau} = \frac{SP}{\eta x} \quad (1)$$

where, x is impregnation length, τ is required time for fully impregnation, S is permeability through fiber bed, P is applied pressure, η is viscosity of resin. From the viewpoint of fully impregnation time τ , Equation (1) is changed to equation (2).

$$\tau = \frac{\eta x^2}{2SP} \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) suggests that some work is effective to get shorter impregnation time of thermoplastic composite as follows; lower viscosity of matrix resin, shorter impregnation length by tow spreading of fibers [4,5], higher permeability of fiber bed by better sizing agents on reinforcement fibers, higher

pressure at impregnation. So in some studies, resins were processed to minute particles [6] or fibers [7-9] to exist near reinforcement fibers to produce thermoplastic composite substrates. And in some studies, matrix resins were melted to get low viscosity by heating at ultimate high temperature without degradation or by special solvent suitable for matrix resin. Therefore thermoplastic composites are relatively expensive to compare with thermosetting composites in spite of low cost resins.

Furthermore, in conventional stamp forming process of thermoplastic composites, infrared (IR) oven is necessary device to preheat materials. There are a few disadvantages by using IR oven in this process. Firstly, the device is relatively expensive. Secondly, materials should be consolidated enough not to separate each layer in the case of laminated composites. Finally, preheating IR oven caused thermal degradation of matrix resin on the surface of composites because materials are easy to damage with heating in the air including oxygen. On the other hand, preheating in vacuum press do not require the consolidation of materials and avoid damage of matrix resin without oxygen atmosphere. Therefore now we are developing vacuum press preheater as high heat efficient device for stamp forming process of thermoplastic composites [10], which can realize to produce a blank of composite panel with impregnation of semi-preg and with preheating material simultaneously for low cost parts of thermoplastic composite materials.

2 EXPERIMENT

2.1 Materials

In this study, we used polypropylene matrix carbon fiber UD prepregs which Mitsubishi Rayon Co., Ltd. manufactured by using TR50S (tensile modulus: 240 GPa, tensile strength: 4900 MPa). Mitsubishi Rayon Co., Ltd. provided us semi-preg (not fully impregnated prepreg) specially for fundamental research about impregnation. Fiber areal weight (FAW) and thickness of thermoplastic prepreg is approximately 75 g/m² and 0.1 mm respectively.

2.2 Preparation of composites

400 kN vacuum hot press as preheating device and 2000 kN hydraulic press for stamp forming were used as shown in Figure 1 and

Figure 2.

Thermoplastic UD prepregs were stacked to prepare cross-ply composite panel with lamination of [0°/90°]_{4s}. And they were melted and pressed in the vacuum hot press. After that, melted materials were took up from the vacuum hot press and compressed rapidly by hydraulic press. In this preheater, air was eliminated by vacuum pump to reduce degradation of matrix resin as shown in Figure 3. Air pressure by our vacuum device was decreased to 300 hPa in 1 minute and to 150 hPa in 2 minutes. We prepared 10 composite panels to investigate preheating and stamp forming conditions as shown in Table 1.

Figure 1: Vacuum press preheater.
(MEIKI CO., LTD.)

Figure 2: Hydraulic press.
(SANKI SEIKO Co., LTD.)

Figure 3: Air pressure in vacuum press preheater.

Table 1: Preheating and stamp forming conditions.

SAMPLE	PREHEATING CONDITIONS			STAMP FORMING CONDITIONS		
	Temperature of mold	Pressure	Time	Temperature of mold	Pressure	Time
	(°C)	(MPa)	(min)	(°C)	(MPa)	(min)
#1	250	0.5	0.5	100	5	1.0
#2	250	0.5	1.0	100	5	1.0
#3	250	1.0	0.5	100	5	1.0
#4	250	1.0	1.0	100	5	1.0
#5	250	0.5	0.5	100	10	1.0
#6	250	0.5	1.0	100	10	1.0
#7	250	1.0	0.5	100	10	1.0
#8	250	1.0	1.0	100	10	1.0
#9	220	1.0	1.0	100	10	1.0
#10	220	1.0	2.0	100	10	1.0

2.3 Fiber content

The weight fraction of carbon fibers in composites was measured by burning them to remove matrix resin. Burning composites was performed by using an electric muffle furnace (HATA ELECTRIC MFG CO., LTD. ELEPOT) in nitrogen atmosphere of 500 °C for 30 minutes. The weight fraction of carbon fibers, W_f is calculated with equation (3), where W_{CF} is the weight of residual carbon fibers after burning test, W_{PPG} is the weight of prepregs before burning test.

$$W_f = \frac{W_{CF}}{W_{PPG}} \quad (3)$$

2.4 Density and void content

The density of composites by electronic densimeter (Alfa Mirage MDS-300) based on Archimedes' principle was used as shown in Equation (4). Specimens were sized 100 mm in length, 15 mm in width and 1.5 mm in thickness. Composite specimens were dried at least 12 hours. After that, density of composite was measured.

$$\rho = \frac{W_A}{W_A - W_B} \times (\rho_0 - d) + d \quad (4)$$

ρ : density of composite
 W_A : weight of composite in air
 W_B : weight of composite in liquid
 ρ_0 : density of liquid
 d : density of air (≈ 0.001 g/cm³)

And also we calculated volume fraction of void (V_{void}) by equation (5) with the density of composite measured by equation (4).

$$\begin{aligned} V_{Void} &= 1 - V_{CF} - V_r \\ &= 1 - \rho \left(\frac{W_{CF}}{\rho_{CF}} + \frac{W_r}{\rho_r} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

V_{void} : volume fraction of void
 V_{CF} : volume fraction of carbon fiber
 V_r : volume fraction of matrix resin
 ρ_{CF} : density of carbon fiber
 ρ_r : density of matrix resin

2.5 Observation of cross-sections

Cross-sections of composites were observed by digital microscope (Keyence VHX-1000) after polishing cut-sections of composites. The degree of impregnation was verified by the observation.

2.6 Evaluation of flexural properties

To measure flexural properties of the prepared composites, 3-point bending tests were conducted by testing machine (SIMADZU AGS-X) with following conditions; distance of supports was 80 mm, cross-head speed of testing machine was 5 mm/min. Size of specimens was the same as that for density measurement. Number of testing was 5 times. The outer layer of cross-ply composites was 0° (along fiber direction) in all 3-point bending test.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Density and void content of composites

Figure 4 is the results of the density of composites and it shows that molding pressure at stamp forming from 5 MPa to 10 MPa and preheating pressure at vacuum press preheater did not affect to density of composites. On the other hand, preheating time gave bigger effects to density of composites. Especially, longer preheating time caused higher density of composites because voids were easily removed by longer impregnation time for semi-impregnated materials. Moreover, to compare “250 °C, 1 MPa, 1 min (#8)” with “220 °C, 1 MPa, 1 min (#9)”, higher temperature preheating induced higher density because the more impregnation was proceeded with lower resin viscosity based on equation

(1). Impregnation time was almost halved by changing higher temperature from 220 °C to 250 °C.

Void content of composites was calculated by equation (5) with weight fraction of carbon fiber and matrix resin. The result of weight fraction of carbon fiber was 61.8 % by burning test with the above mentioned condition. This indicated weight fraction of matrix resin was 39.2 %. The density of carbon fiber and polypropylene as matrix resin were 1.82 g/cm³ and 0.91 g/cm³ respectively for equation (5). Figure 5 is the result of void content of composites prepared by different vacuum press preheater and hydraulic press conditions. It shows that longer preheating conditions and higher temperature conditions caused lower void content corresponding with the density of composites. Molding pressure of stamp forming did not affect to density and void content so much.

Figure 4: Density of composites prepared by different preheating and stamp forming conditions.

Figure 5: Void content of composites by different preheating and stamp forming conditions.

3.2 Observation of cross-sections

Figure 6 is the cross-section of original semi-preg and it shows matrix resin of the substrates was

not fully impregnated and contained many voids and resin rich regions. Figure 7 to 9 are cross-sections of composite prepared by different preheating conditions. Corresponding to calculated void content, longer time and higher temperature preheating caused lower void content of composite made of semi-pregs.

Figure 6: Original semi-preg.

Figure 7: Composite #7 prepared by 250 °C, 1 MPa, 0.5 min preheating.

Figure 8: Composite #8 prepared by 250 °C, 1 MPa, 1 min preheating.

Figure 9: Composite #9 prepared by 220 °C, 1 MPa, 1 min preheating.

3.2 Mechanical property of composites

Figure 10 is the result of flexural strength of cross-ply laminated composite prepared by different preheating and stamp forming conditions. The coefficients of variation of all composites were from 3 % to 6 %. Figure 10 shows that longer preheating conditions and higher temperature conditions caused higher strength. The result of flexural strength has relatively same tendency as density of composite. To compare “250 °C, 0.5 MPa, 0.5 min preheating (#5)” with “250 °C, 0.5 MPa, 1 min preheating (#6)”, shorter preheating time caused 15 % decrease of flexural strength. This result indicates that composite materials should contain lower void content to get higher mechanical property in the case of this lamination.

Figure 11 is the result of flexural modulus of cross-ply composites. The coefficients of variation of flexural modulus were very small, within 3 % for all composites. To compare all composites by different preheating and stamp forming conditions, flexural modulus of them was almost the same, differences were within 2 %. This result indicates flexural modulus of cross-ply laminated composite was difficult to correspond to composites with low void content less than 2 %.

Figure 10: Flexural strength of composite by different preheating and stamp forming conditions.

Figure 11: Flexural modulus of composite by different preheating and stamp forming conditions.

4 CONCLUSIONS

We prepared several composite panels to investigate preheating and stamp forming conditions by using vacuum press preheater and hydraulic press. Preheating conditions were more effective than stamp forming conditions in the case of composite panels of semi-preg. Especially preheating time was the most effective factor to compare with other factors. For cross-ply laminated composites containing a few percent voids, Flexural strength of them was decreased 15 %. On the other hand, flexural modulus of all composites was almost the same. This result indicated flexural strength was more sensitive property than flexural modulus for low void thermoplastic composites.

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